

EVALUATION OF STRENGTH OF LAMINATES IN A BIAxIAL STATE OF STRESS, BY MEANS OF A SELECTIVE PROGRESSIVE FAILURE CRITERION

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ABSTRACT

Progressive failure in fibre reinforced composite materials is studied by means of the finite element method. During increasing load, different stages of damage can be distinguished, from first-ply failure up to ultimate failure. The occurrence of failure is predicted by the Tsai-Wu failure criterion, while the actual mode of failure, such as fibre failure or matrix failure, is determined by a comparative stress-criterion. Dependent on the type of failure the finite element model is updated as for the material properties in the concerning elements and the modified model is subjected to a new analysis. This procedure is repeated up to final failure by means of the finite element package Ansys5.0a.

The applied method is explained on the basis of the analysis of an elementary model. Finally, propagation of failure is shown by the results of the analysis of a laminated specimen containing a hole.

The agreement between analytical prediction and experimental results is excellent.

INTRODUCTION

Failure of multidirectional laminates composed of glass-fibre reinforced polyester has been studied by means of biaxial tests on flat cross-shaped specimen provided with a small circular hole in the centre. According to [1], the ultimate laminate strength is nearly three times as high as the level where first-ply failure was predicted according to the Tsai-Wu criterion. The experimental results illustrate the importance of the phenomenon of progressive failure and the need of an easy accessible computational tool.

In order to predict the ultimate strength of laminates in a biaxial state of stress, a straight-on computational method is proposed based on a linear solving method. The laminate is loaded to a level where first-ply failure occurs and the stresses at the critical location are determined in order to select the type of failure. Depending on the local stress situation, the material properties are modified corresponding with the type of failure, and a new run is started in order to determine the next element to fail. Moreover, the local effects of damage are important in relation to the redistribution of stresses.

This concept is elaborated with the finite element package Ansys(5.0a), where an updated Tsai-Wu failure criterion is available for layered SHELL99 elements. The computational procedure is managed through the Ansys Parametric Design Language (APDL), described in the

manual as: 'APDL extends the Ansys command language to reduce the user input and/or user interaction requirements in performing finite element analyses'. This powerful feature enables the selection of the type of failure, the modification of the element properties and the complete control of repeated runs.

The proposed computational method is based on a standard usage of the finite element package Ansys, without the necessity to implement special developed non-linear modules.

At this stage only two types of failure are distinguished, selected by one stress criterion. This can be extended easily, in order to perform parametric studies, aiming to fit theoretical and experimental results.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

In order to predict first-ply failure, the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is applied, formulated in tensor notation as

$$F_i \cdot \sigma_i + F_{ij} \cdot \sigma_i \cdot \sigma_j = 1 \quad (1)$$

which can be worked out for plane stress in an orthotropic layer as

$$F_1 \cdot \sigma_1 + F_2 \cdot \sigma_2 + F_6 \cdot \sigma_6 + F_{11} \cdot \sigma_1^2 + F_{22} \cdot \sigma_2^2 + F_{66} \cdot \sigma_6^2 + 2F_{12} \cdot \sigma_1 \cdot \sigma_2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

where $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6)$ are the stresses in fibre direction.

F_i and F_{ij} can be expressed in the unidirectional strength values:

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{X_t} + \frac{1}{X_c} \quad F_{11} = -\frac{1}{X_t \cdot X_c}$$

$$F_2 = \frac{1}{Y_t} + \frac{1}{Y_c} \quad F_{22} = -\frac{1}{Y_t \cdot Y_c}$$

$$F_6 = 0 \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{S^2}$$

where X_t and X_c represents respectively the tensile and compressive strength in 1-direction, Y_t and Y_c the tensile and compressive strength in 2-direction, and S the shear strength.

Assumed is $F_{12} = -0.5\sqrt{F_{11} \cdot F_{22}}$ as suggested by Tsai-Hahn [2].

The inverse of the 'strength ratio' $\xi_3 = 1/S_f$ can be derived by substituting $S_f(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6)$ into Eqn (2), and solving the linear quadratic equation in S_f , so

$$\xi_3 = 1 / \left(-\frac{B}{2A} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{B}{2A}\right)^2 + 1/A} \right) \quad (3)$$

where:

$$A = F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_{66}\sigma_6^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 \quad (4)$$

$$B = F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 \quad (5)$$

In Ansys5.0a the variable ξ_3 is calculated for each layer of the SHELL99 element and can be accessed by ETABLE variable NMIS(2).

First-ply failure is assumed to occur in the layer where $\xi_3 = 1$.

To determine the type of failure, the stress levels in fibre direction and perpendicular to the fibres, defined in Eqn (6) and Eqn (7) by α_1 and α_2 , have to be compared.

The factors α_1 and α_2 are different for tensile and compressive stresses in Eqn (6) and Eqn (7).

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\sigma_1}{f_{1t}} \quad (\sigma_1 \geq 0); \quad \alpha_1 = -\frac{\sigma_1}{f_{1c}} \quad (\sigma_1 < 0) \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{f_{2t}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_6}{f_6}\right)^2} \quad (\sigma_2 \geq 0); \quad \alpha_2 = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{f_{2c}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_6}{f_6}\right)^2} \quad (\sigma_2 < 0) \quad (7)$$

If $\alpha_1 > \alpha_2$ fibre failure is assumed to occur, else matrix failure.

ANALYSIS OF AN ELEMENTARY MODEL

A symmetrical laminate $(0, \pm 45^\circ)_s$ is modelled by overlapping SHELL99 elements (8-nodal isoparametric), where each layer direction is identified by a different element type number. So, the number of layers of each element is restricted to 1. This choice facilitates selective procedures.

Three element types are defined:

type 1: $\theta_1 = 0^\circ \quad t_1 = 1\text{mm}$

type 2: $\theta_2 = +45^\circ \quad t_2 = 0.5\text{mm}$

type 3: $\theta_3 = -45^\circ \quad t_3 = 0.5\text{mm}$

The material properties are the same for all layers, and listed in Table 1. (Units N/mm^2)

Table 1.

	Material 1 Undamaged	Material 2 Inter-fibre failure	Material 3 Fibre-failure
E_1	26650	26650	.01
E_2	4950	49.5	.01
G_{12}	1430	14.3	.01
ν_{12}	0.043	.00043	0.3
f_{1t}	430	430	10^6
f_{1c}	-470	-470	-10^6
f_{2t}	44	10^6	10^6
f_{2c}	-163	-10^6	-10^6
f_6	80	10^6	10^6

Note that in Ansys the Poison-ratio ν_{xy} is defined as contraction in x-direction caused by σ_y , where Ansys deviates from the general used definition.

The strength value in failed direction is increased to 10^6 , compared to the undamaged material, to avoid the same type of failure to occur again.

Material 3 is a dummy material, with very low stiffness and very high strength. The use of a dummy material is important in analyses of non-symmetrical laminates, where the z-location of all layers are involved.

The most simple structural model is a square with symmetrical constraints along x- and y-axis, covered by three overlapping elements with the mentioned fibre directions.

Two examples are worked out, respectively loaded as shown in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b.

Displacement is applied to a level where first-ply failure will be found in a particular layer ($\xi_3 = 1$). The type of failure is selected by the stress criterion discussed in the previous chapter.

Dependant on the diagnosed failure type, the material properties of the concerning layer will be modified. Subsequently a new analysis will be performed based on the modified properties.

Figure 1. Elementary models, loaded by displacement

In that new run, the first displacement equals the displacement in the previous run. This load step is used to determine the displacement which is necessary to apply, in order to achieve a value $\xi_3 = 1$ and find the next failure.

The described procedure is analogue to displacement controlled tests, resulting in a more stable process as can be achieved by load control. It can be performed in Ansys in a loop-construction by means of APDL.

The result of the analysis, caused by uni-axial loading u_x , is depicted in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. σ - ϵ diagram for element loading u_x

At Mark 1, first-ply failure is calculated in the 0° -layer, where failure of fibres occurs. Next failure is found by inter-fibre failure in the $\pm 45^\circ$ -layers at Mark 2, and final failure (not drawn) at $\epsilon_x = 7.549$ where all layers are failed by fibre failure.

The behaviour of an element loaded in both x- and y-direction is depicted in Fig. 3.

In this case first-ply failure occurs in the $\pm 45^\circ$ -layers by inter-fibre failure at Mark 1, directly followed by inter-fibre failure in the 0° -layer at Mark 2. Then fibre failure occurs in the 0° -layer at Mark 3, and finally the $\pm 45^\circ$ -layers fail at Mark 4.

The main difference towards the first example is the lower level of first ply failure, due to the loading in y-direction. On the other hand there is very little difference in the level of final failure.

The results of these elementary analyses have been compared with the results obtained with other available computational tools such as 'Think Composites' [3], and 'Comlin94' [4].

Figure 3. σ - ϵ diagram for element loading $\{u_x, u_y = \frac{1}{2}u_x\}$

ANALYSIS OF UNIAXIAL SPECIMEN WITH HOLE

The same procedure as has been described for a single element is applied to a finite element model of a laminated specimen with a centre hole. The laminate lay-up is the same as used in the elementary examples. The length/width ratio of the specimen is four. For reasons of symmetry, only one quarter of the structure is been used. The model, loaded by displacement in X-direction is represented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Model of a laminated specimen with hole

At the end of each analysis all elements conditioned by $\xi_3 \geq 0.99$ are selected, and modified depending on the type of failure determined by selective stress criteria. In the next run, first the same displacement is applied as in the previous run, in order to determine the next displacement necessary to achieve the maximum ξ_3 to equal 1. If this displacement should be smaller than the previous one, the displacement will not be altered, enabling a continued propagation of failure at the same strain rate.

In Fig. 5 the result of a full analysis of the specimen is depicted, where $\epsilon_x = \frac{u_x}{l}$.

First-ply failure appears by matrix failure in the 0° -layer at a strain $\epsilon_x = 0.00186$.

Until $\epsilon_x = 0.00525$ the stress σ_x increases till a maximum $\sigma_x = 70 \text{ N/mm}^2$, and matrix cracking is propagating in all three layers.

Figure 5. σ - ϵ diagram of specimen containing a hole

The propagation of failure is monitored in Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, for different levels of strain, for fibre directions 0° , $+45^\circ$ and -45° from left to right in each figure.

Figure 6. Propagation of failure, $\epsilon(x) = 0.309 \%$

Figure 7. $\epsilon(x) = 0.523 \%$

When $\epsilon_x = 0.00525$, the first element with fibre failure is detected, appearing in the $+45^\circ$ -layer. At the same time the maximum value of σ_x has been reached.

So, first fibre failure coincides with ultimate failure of the structure, as can be read from Fig. 5. The propagation after first fibre failure is depicted in Fig. 8, showing propagation of fibre failure in the $+45^\circ$ -layer.

Figure 8. Final failure $\epsilon(x) = 0.525 \%$

The ratio of stress-level at ultimate failure and first-ply failure equals 2.70, which is in good agreement with experimental results as mentioned in the introduction.

CONCLUSIONS

The main advantage of the described method is the simplicity, because it is not necessary to implement any specific non-linear modules to describe the degraded material properties after failure. The applied method is very stable, because linear solving techniques have been used. The computational results are in agreement with experimental results as for determining ultimate failure of biaxial specimen with a centre hole, composed of glass-fibre reinforced polyester. The study will be extended to other types of failure and other composites and refinement of several computational parameters will be made.

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